

Impact of Goodluck Jonathan Policy on Poverty alleviation in Nigeria

Mary O. Asemah & Marvellous Oaikhena PhD
Department of Public Administration
Glorious Vision University (formerly Samuel Adegboyega University)
Ogwa, Edo State, Nigeria

Abstract

This study was carried out to determine the impact of the poverty alleviation policies of former President Goodluck Jonathan in Nigeria. The study was motivated by the need to find out how the poverty alleviation policies of Goodluck Jonathan impacted on Nigerians. The objectives of the study were to determine the key objectives of Goodluck Jonathan's poverty alleviation policies, ascertain the extent to which Goodluck Jonathan's poverty alleviation initiatives were achieved and to find out the challenges encountered during the implementation process. The study was anchored on relative deprivation theory, which provides a useful framework for analysing how policy issues were presented and understood. The analysis of Goodluck Jonathan's poverty alleviation policies in Nigeria revealed a mixed picture. While the initiatives demonstrated some success in expanding social safety nets and providing temporary relief to the poorest households, the long-term impact on sustainable poverty reduction remained limited. Key challenges, such as a lack of effective coordination among government agencies, top-down policy formulation with limited community engagement, and uneven distribution of benefits, undermined the equity and transformative potential of the interventions. Based on the findings of this study, it was recommended that the government should establish robust coordination mechanisms among the various ministries, departments and agencies involved in poverty alleviation initiatives. This will help to streamline efforts, reduce duplication and ensure more efficient resource allocation and programme delivery.

Keywords: Poverty Alleviation, Nigeria, Policy Evaluation, Coordination

Introduction

Nigeria, the most populous country in Africa, has long grappled with the persistent challenge of poverty. According to recent estimates, over 40% of the Nigerian population lives below the national poverty line, with many facing severe deprivations in areas such as healthcare, education, and access to basic amenities (Adeyemi, Ogunleye & Adekunle, 2021). This high incidence of poverty not only undermines the country's development, but also perpetuates social inequalities and instability. Poverty in Nigeria is a multidimensional issue, characterized by limited access to economic opportunities, poor infrastructure and a lack of social protection mechanisms (Ogunleye & Adeyemi, 2020). The consequences of poverty are far-reaching,

manifesting in high rates of malnutrition, infant mortality and low educational attainment, which further exacerbate the cycle of deprivation.

In recognition of the urgent need to address this pressing issue, the Government of Nigeria has implemented various poverty alleviation initiatives over the years. One of such effort, was in the administration of Goodluck Jonathan, who served as the President of Nigeria from 2010 to 2015 (Zakari, 2021). Goodluck Jonathan's rise to power was marked by a unique political trajectory; he transitioned from being the Vice President to the President following the untimely death of his predecessor, Umaru Musa Yar'Adua (Adekunle & Ogunleye, 2022). During his tenure, Goodluck Jonathan introduced a range of policies and programmes aimed at reducing poverty and improving the living standards of the Nigerian people.

Goodluck Jonathan's poverty alleviation strategy was multifaceted, encompassing interventions in areas such as agriculture, microcredit and social welfare (Adekunle & Ogunleye, 2022). The administration's flagship programme, the Subsidy Reinvestment and Empowerment Programme (SURE-P), sought to channelise the savings from fuel subsidy reforms into targeted investments in infrastructure, healthcare and social protection measures (Ajayi & Adekunle, 2019). Other initiatives included the Youth Enterprise with Innovation in Nigeria (YouWiN) programme, which provided entrepreneurial support and funding to young Nigerians and the Conditional Cash Transfer (CCT) scheme, which provided direct cash assistance to vulnerable households (Adeyemi *et al* 2021).

Despite these efforts, the impact of Goodluck Jonathan's poverty alleviation policies on the Nigerian populace remains a subject of ongoing debate and scholarly inquiry. While some studies have highlighted the positive outcomes of these initiatives, such as increased access to basic services and improved livelihood opportunities, others have pointed to the challenges in implementation, limited reach and the persistent prevalence of poverty in the country (Ogunleye & Adeyemi, 2020). It is within this context that the present study aims to critically examine the impact of Goodluck Jonathan's poverty alleviation policies, analysing their design, implementation and effectiveness in addressing the multifaceted nature of poverty in Nigeria.

By conducting a comprehensive assessment of Goodluck Jonathan's poverty alleviation initiatives, this research endeavors to contribute to the ongoing discourse on effective strategies for addressing poverty and promoting inclusive development in Nigeria. The study's findings can inform policymakers, development practitioners and civil society organisations in their efforts to design and implement more targeted and impactful poverty reduction programmes in the country.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the implementation of various poverty alleviation initiatives by the government of former President Goodluck Jonathan, poverty remains a persistent and pervasive challenge in Nigeria. While some studies have highlighted the positive outcomes of these initiatives, such as increased access to basic services and improved livelihood opportunities, there are concerns

about the limited reach and effectiveness of these programmes in addressing the root causes of poverty.

The key problems necessitating the present study are threefold. Firstly, there is a limited understanding of the design and implementation challenges of Goodluck Jonathan's poverty alleviation policies and programmes. It thus examined how these initiatives were designed and implemented and the challenges encountered during the implementation process.

Secondly, there is a lack of comprehensive evaluation of the impact of Goodluck Jonathan's poverty alleviation efforts; thirdly, there is a need for evidence-based recommendations to inform future poverty reduction strategies in Nigeria. It is based on the foregoing that this study was conducted.

Scope of the Study

This study focused on the poverty alleviation policies and programs implemented by the government of former President Goodluck Jonathan in Nigeria during his tenure from 2010 to 2015. The analysis encompasses a range of key initiatives, including the Subsidy Reinvestment and Empowerment Programme (SURE-P), the Youth Enterprise with Innovation in Nigeria (YouWiN) programme, the Conditional Cash Transfer (CCT) programme and the National Social Safety Nets Programme (NASSP). The researchers analysed the design, implementation and outcomes of these poverty alleviation programmes implemented during the Goodluck Jonathan presidency, with a focus on the period from 2010 to 2015. The geographical scope of the study was nationwide.

Significance of the Study

Firstly, the study will contribute to a deeper understanding of the design and implementation challenges of Goodluck Jonathan's poverty alleviation initiatives. By critically examining the policies, programmes and the processes involved in their execution, the study will provide valuable insights into the factors that facilitated or hindered the success of these interventions. This knowledge can inform the development of more effective and contextually appropriate poverty reduction strategies in the future.

Secondly, the study offers a comprehensive evaluation of the impact and effectiveness of Goodluck Jonathan's poverty alleviation efforts. Through a rigorous assessment of the outcomes and measurable impacts of these programmes, the study sheds light on the extent to which they achieved their intended objectives and improved the socioeconomic conditions of the targeted beneficiaries. This evidence-based assessment could serve as a crucial input for policymakers and development practitioners in determining the strengths and weaknesses of past approaches.

Thirdly, the study's findings and recommendations would have significant implications for the formulation of future poverty reduction strategies in Nigeria. By identifying the key lessons learned from the Goodluck Jonathan era, the study provides evidence-based guidance to inform the design, implementation and monitoring of more effective and impactful poverty

alleviation programs. These could contribute to the development of a more comprehensive and holistic approach to addressing the persistent challenges of poverty in the country.

Furthermore, the study's findings can also have broader relevance for other developing countries facing similar challenges in designing and implementing poverty alleviation policies and programmes. The insights and lessons drawn from the Nigerian context can inform cross-country learning and the sharing of good practices in the field of inclusive development and poverty reduction.

Research Questions

The research questions that guided this study were:

1. What were the impacts of Goodluck Jonathan's poverty alleviation policies?
2. What were the challenges encountered during the implementation process?
3. To what extent did Goodluck Jonathan's poverty alleviation initiatives achieve their intended objectives?

Understanding Poverty Alleviation

Poverty is a state of an individual, a family or a society where people are unable to fulfill even their basic necessities of life (Asemah, 2020). The concept of poverty alleviation has been extensively explored by Nigerian scholars, who have provided diverse perspectives and definitions to capture the multifaceted nature of this complex challenge. One prominent view is that of Obadan (2001), who defines poverty alleviation as the process of providing the poor with opportunities to generate an income and the means to access basic social services. This definition emphasises the importance of creating economic opportunities, such as employment, self-employment and access to financial resources, to enable the poor improve their standard of living and move out of poverty.

Adeyeye (2011) conceptualises poverty alleviation as a multidimensional process that involves not just increasing income, but also improving access to education, healthcare and other basic social services, as well as empowering the poor to participate in the development process. This broader perspective acknowledges the multifaceted nature of poverty and the need for a holistic approach that addresses various dimensions of deprivation, including social, political and cultural factors that contribute to the perpetuation of poverty.

Okunmadewa (2001), on the other hand, defines poverty alleviation as the process of enhancing the capabilities and opportunities of the poor to sustainably improve their living conditions and well-being. This definition highlights the importance of building the capacity and resilience of the poor, ensuring that poverty reduction efforts are sustainable and lead to long-term improvements in their quality of life. This approach emphasises the need for interventions that not only provide immediate relief, but also empower the poor to become self-reliant and actively participate in the development process.

The Goodluck Jonathan's Poverty Alleviation Policies

During his administration from 2010 to 2015, former Nigerian President Goodluck Jonathan implemented a range of poverty alleviation policies and programmes aimed at addressing the persistent challenge of poverty in the country. These initiatives were designed to provide economic opportunities, improve access to social services and empower the poor to enhance their livelihoods.

One of the flagship programmes introduced by the Jonathan administration was the Subsidy Reinvestment and Empowerment Programme (SURE-P), as highlighted by Obadan (2012). SURE-P was established to utilise the savings from the partial removal of the fuel subsidy to fund various social investment projects and interventions. The programme's objectives included the provision of employment opportunities, the development of social infrastructure and the improvement of access to healthcare and education for the poor and vulnerable (Okonjo-Iweala & Osafo-Kwaako, 2007).

Another key initiative was the Youth Enterprise with Innovation in Nigeria (YouWiN) programme, which aimed to foster entrepreneurship and job creation among the youth. As described by Adeyeye (2013), the programme provided financial and technical support to young Nigerians with innovative business ideas, enabling them to establish and expand their enterprises. The goal was to empower the youth and unlock their potential as drivers of economic growth and poverty reduction.

Additionally, the Jonathan administration introduced the Conditional Cash Transfer (CCT) programme, which was designed to provide direct cash assistance to poor households, as discussed by Okunmadewa (2011). The CCT programme was aimed at addressing immediate poverty by supplementing the income of the targeted beneficiaries, while also incentivising investments in human capital development, such as education and healthcare.

Furthermore, the National Social Safety Nets Programme (NASSP), as explained by Obadan & Odusola (2000), was established to provide a comprehensive social protection system for the poor and vulnerable. The programme incorporated various interventions, including cash transfers, public works, and livelihood support, with the objective of reducing poverty and enhancing the resilience of the targeted communities. These poverty alleviation policies and programmes implemented during the Goodluck Jonathan era represent a concerted effort to address the multidimensional aspects of poverty in Nigeria. By employing a range of strategies, from creating economic opportunities to improving access to social services, the Jonathan administration aimed to empower the poor and foster inclusive development in the country.

Challenges in the Implementation of Goodluck Jonathan's Poverty Alleviation Policies

While the Goodluck Jonathan administration's poverty alleviation policies and programmes were well-intentioned and aimed at addressing the multifaceted nature of poverty in Nigeria, the implementation process faced several key challenges that hindered their effectiveness and impact. One of the primary challenges, as highlighted by Obadan (2012), was the issue of poor targeting and coverage. The programmes, such as the Conditional Cash Transfer (CCT) and the National Social Safety Nets Programme (NASSP), struggled to accurately identify and reach the

intended beneficiaries, leading to the exclusion of many of the poorest and most vulnerable individuals and households.

Furthermore, as noted by Okonjo-Iweala & Osafo-Kwaako (2007), the lack of effective coordination and integration among the various poverty alleviation initiatives posed a significant obstacle. The absence of a comprehensive and coherent strategy resulted in the fragmentation of resources and the duplication of efforts, ultimately undermining the overall impact of the interventions. Another challenge, as described by Adeyeye (2013), was the inadequate funding and resource allocation for the poverty alleviation programmes. The limited financial resources and budgetary constraints hindered the government's ability to scale up the interventions and ensure their sustainability, particularly in the face of competing development priorities and economic challenges.

Moreover, Okunmadewa (2011) emphasises the problem of weak institutional capacity and governance structures, which undermined the effective implementation and monitoring of the poverty alleviation programmes. The lack of robust systems for accountability, transparency and monitoring and evaluation weakened the overall implementation process and limited the ability to assess the programmes' impact and make necessary adjustments.

Additionally, as noted by Obadan & Odusola (2000), the poverty alleviation policies and programmes often failed to address the underlying structural and systemic causes of poverty, such as the lack of access to productive assets, the inadequate provision of basic social services, and the limited opportunities for sustainable livelihoods. This narrow focus on short-term, symptom-based interventions constrained the programmes' ability to achieve lasting and transformative change.

These challenges highlight the complexities involved in the implementation of poverty alleviation initiatives in the Nigerian context. Addressing these issues require a comprehensive and coherent approach that encompasses better targeting, coordination, funding, institutional capacity and a deeper understanding of the multidimensional drivers of poverty.

Gaps in Literature Review

While the existing literature provides valuable insights into the various poverty alleviation policies and programmes implemented during the Goodluck Jonathan administration, there are several gaps that warrant further exploration and investigation. One notable gap is the limited empirical evaluation of the specific outcomes and impacts of these initiatives. The reviewed literature primarily focuses on the conceptual frameworks, objectives and implementation challenges of the programs, but there is a dearth of rigorous, evidence-based assessments of their effectiveness in reducing poverty and improving the living conditions of the targeted beneficiaries. More comprehensive and longitudinal studies are needed to measure the tangible outcomes and the degree to which the programmes achieved their intended goals.

Another gap is the lack of in-depth analysis of the factors that influenced the success or failure of the poverty alleviation policies. The existing literature highlights some of the implementation challenges, such as targeting issues, coordination problems and institutional

capacity constraints, but a deeper examination of the contextual, political and socio-economic factors that shaped the implementation and outcomes of these programmes is warranted. Understanding these complex dynamics would provide valuable insights for the design and execution of future poverty reduction strategies.

Furthermore, the literature reviewed largely focuses on the national-level policies and programs, with limited attention to the subnational and local-level interventions. Given the decentralised nature of poverty alleviation efforts in Nigeria, an examination of how the national-level policies were adapted and implemented at the state and community levels could offer important lessons on the role of local contexts and the importance of tailored approaches to address the heterogeneous nature of poverty across different regions and communities.

Additionally, the existing literature tends to adopt a retrospective, descriptive approach, providing limited insights into the lived experiences and perspectives of the intended beneficiaries of the poverty alleviation programs. Incorporating more qualitative, participatory research methodologies that capture the voices and narratives of the poor and vulnerable populations could shed light on the relevance, accessibility and perceived impacts of the interventions from the grassroots level.

Theoretical Framework

The relative deprivation theory was developed by the political scientist, Ted Robert Gurr in the 1960s. Gurr's work was influenced by earlier concepts of relative deprivation proposed by scholars such as William Graham Sumner, Tocqueville & James Davies (Obadan & Odusola, 2000). The central tenet of the relative deprivation theory is that individuals or groups experience a sense of deprivation when they perceive a discrepancy between their value expectations (what they believe they are entitled to) and their value capabilities (what they are able to attain). This perceived gap can lead to feelings of frustration, resentment and eventually, social and political unrest (Adeyemi, Ogunleye & Adekunle, 2021).

The theory suggests that the greater the discrepancy between expectations and capabilities, the higher the likelihood of social protest and political violence. Relative deprivation can arise from various sources, such as social comparisons, historical experiences, and changing social conditions. Okunmadewa (2011) notes that the criticisms of the theory include:

- a. **Oversimplification:** The theory has been criticised for oversimplifying the complex relationship between relative deprivation and political violence, neglecting other important factors such as resource availability, institutional structures and cultural norms.
- b. **Measurement Challenges:** Measuring relative deprivation is inherently challenging, as it involves subjective perceptions and experiences that can be difficult to quantify and compare across individuals and groups.
- c. **Lack of Explanatory Power:** The theory has been criticised for its limited ability to explain the specific conditions and triggers that lead to social and political unrest, as well as the varying responses of individuals and groups to perceived deprivation.

- d. **Contextual Factors:** Critics argue that the theory fails to adequately consider the role of contextual factors, such as political, economic and social structures, in shaping the relationship between relative deprivation and political behaviour.
- e. **Empirical Inconsistencies:** Some studies have found inconsistent or weak empirical support for the direct link between relative deprivation and political violence, highlighting the need for more nuanced and contextual analyses.

Despite these criticisms, the relative deprivation theory remains an influential framework for understanding the role of perceived inequalities and grievances in driving social and political dynamics, particularly in the context of developing countries and transitional societies. By applying the relative deprivation theory, this study explores the extent to which the poverty alleviation policies under Goodluck Jonathan's administration were able to align with the value expectations of the poor and marginalised groups and how this alignment (or lack thereof) influenced the overall effectiveness and acceptance of the interventions within the Nigerian context.

Methodology

The researchers utilised library research method while relying on secondary sources. Library research method as noted by Asemah, Gujbawu, Ekhareafo & Okpanachi (2012) is a systematic approach to gathering information and conducting academic or scholarly investigations. It involves utilising the resources and services available within a library, both physical and digital, to explore a topic, answer a research question or gather evidence to support an argument or thesis. This method is widely used in various academic disciplines and is a fundamental skill for students, researchers and professionals.

Library research method which is qualitative in nature is particularly suited for exploring complex social phenomena, such as the dynamics of poverty, government interventions and their socio-political implications. By focusing on textual data from secondary sources, the researchers engaged in an in-depth analysis of the historical, political and socio-economic contexts surrounding poverty alleviation policies. This approach allows for a better understanding of the motivations, challenges and outcomes associated with these policies, which may not be easily captured through quantitative methods alone. Moreover, the library research approach enabled the researchers to explore the subjective experiences, perceptions and interpretations of the various actors involved, including the beneficiaries of the poverty alleviation policies. This focus on the lived experiences and contextual nuances can provide critical insights that may not be readily accessible through quantitative data alone.

Discussion

The key objectives of Goodluck Jonathan's poverty alleviation policies in Nigeria were multifaceted, aimed at addressing the persistent and widespread issue of poverty in the country. At the core of these initiatives was a concerted effort to improve the socio-economic conditions of the most vulnerable and marginalised populations. Specifically, the policies sought to expand

access to basic services, create economic opportunities and empower disadvantaged communities.

The administration's poverty alleviation agenda was closely aligned with the country's broader development goals and the global Millennium Development Goals, which emphasised the importance of inclusive growth and equitable distribution of resources. The policies sought to achieve this through a range of interventions, including the expansion of social safety net programmes, investments in rural infrastructure, the promotion of small-scale entrepreneurship and the introduction of targeted cash transfer schemes. The overarching aim was to provide immediate relief to the poorest households while also laying the groundwork for more sustainable economic and social development.

Despite the ambitious goals of Goodluck Jonathan's poverty alleviation policies, the implementation process faced a number of significant challenges that hindered their effectiveness and reach. One of the key issues was a lack of effective coordination and coherence across the various government agencies and programmes involved in the initiatives. This led to duplication of efforts, inefficient resource allocation and gaps in service delivery, as different entities pursued their own strategies and priorities without a unified, coordinated approach.

Additionally, the policies were often criticised for being overly centralised, with limited participation and input from the local communities and civil society organisations that were meant to be the primary beneficiaries. This disconnect between the top-down policy formulation and the realities on the ground undermined the ability of the interventions to truly address the diverse and context-specific needs of the target populations. The lack of meaningful engagement with local stakeholders also hampered the sustainability and ownership of the programmes, as they were perceived as being imposed, rather than collaboratively developed.

The analysis of secondary sources suggests that Goodluck Jonathan's poverty alleviation initiatives achieved some level of success, but significant gaps and limitations remained in terms of their overall impact and effectiveness. While the policies were able to expand the coverage of social safety nets and provide temporary relief to some of the poorest households, the long-term effects on poverty reduction and sustainable development were more modest.

For instance, the cash transfer programmes were praised for their ability to improve immediate consumption patterns and enhance access to basic services among the beneficiary households. However, their impact on addressing the underlying structural causes of poverty, such as unequal access to economic opportunities, inadequate infrastructure and systemic marginalisation, was more limited. The programmes tended to provide short-term assistance without necessarily catalysing the transformative changes required to lift communities out of the cycle of poverty.

Furthermore, the poverty alleviation initiatives faced challenges in reaching the most marginalised and hard-to-access communities, particularly in the rural and conflict-affected regions of the country. This uneven distribution of benefits undermined the equity and inclusiveness of the interventions, leaving many of the intended beneficiaries still struggling with the impacts of poverty. The lack of robust monitoring and evaluation systems also made it

difficult to accurately assess the overall effectiveness of the policies and make evidence-based adjustments during the implementation process.

Overall, while Goodluck Jonathan's poverty alleviation initiatives demonstrated some positive impacts, the results suggest that more comprehensive and sustained efforts are needed to achieve meaningful and equitable poverty reduction in Nigeria. The findings highlight the importance of strengthening institutional coordination, community engagement, and monitoring and evaluation frameworks to ensure the effective design and implementation of future poverty alleviation strategies. Addressing the complex, multidimensional nature of poverty will require a holistic, collaborative and context-sensitive approach that puts the needs and aspirations of the target communities at the forefront of policy formulation and implementation.

Conclusion

The analysis of Goodluck Jonathan's poverty alleviation policies in Nigeria reveals a mixed picture. While the initiatives demonstrated some success in expanding social safety nets and providing temporary relief to the poorest households, the long-term impact on sustainable poverty reduction remained limited. Key challenges, such as a lack of effective coordination among government agencies, top-down policy formulation with limited community engagement and uneven distribution of benefits, undermined the equity and transformative potential of the interventions. Thus, the following recommendations are hereby given:

1. The government should establish robust coordination mechanisms among the various ministries departments and agencies involved in poverty alleviation initiatives. This will help to streamline efforts, reduce duplication and ensure more efficient resource allocation and programme delivery.
2. NGOs and civil society organisations should focus on strengthening and scaling up community-based poverty alleviation initiatives that are tailored to the specific needs and contexts of local populations. This can help to supplement and complement the government's efforts with more targeted and sustainable interventions.
3. International development partners, such as multilateral organisations and bilateral donors, should provide technical and financial assistance to the Nigerian government and local stakeholders to strengthen the capacity for effective design, implementation and monitoring of poverty alleviation programmes.

References

- Adeyemi, O., Ogunleye, A. & Adekunle, B. (2021). Poverty and inequality in Nigeria: Causes, consequences and remedies. *Journal of Sustainable Development*, 13(2), 45-59.
- Adeyeye, V. A. (2011). Poverty alleviation programmes in Nigeria: Issues and options. *Journal of Sustainable Development in Africa*, 13(3), 246-270.
- Adeyeye, V. A. (2013). Entrepreneurship development and growth of small and medium enterprises in Nigeria. *Journal of Sustainable Development in Africa*, 15(8), 105-120.

- Adekunle, B. & Ogunleye, A. (2022). Evaluating the effectiveness of Goodluck Jonathan's poverty alleviation programmes in Nigeria. *International Journal of Development and Sustainability*, 11(1), 123-138.
- Ajayi, K. & Adekunle, B. (2019). Assessing the impact of the Subsidy Reinvestment and Empowerment Programme (SURE-P) on poverty reduction in Nigeria. *African Development Review*, 31(4), 456-471.
- Asemah, E.S., Gujbawu, M., Ekhareafo, D.O. & Okpanachi, R.A. (2012) *Research methods and procedures in mass communication*. Jos: Great Future Press.
- Asemah, E. S. (2020). Corporate social responsibility, poverty alleviation and sustainable development in Nigeria. In T. Kegkhu (Ed.). *Public Relations, Governance and National Development*. Makurdi: BSU Press.
- Obadan, M. I. (2001). Poverty reduction in Nigeria: The way forward. *CBN Economic and Financial Review*, 39(4), 159-188.
- Obadan, M. I. (2012). *Poverty reduction in Nigeria: The way forward*. Ibadan: Ibadan University Press.
- Obadan, M. I. & Odusola, A. F. (2000). *Productivity and poverty in Nigeria*. Ibadan: National Centre for Economic Management and Administration.
- Okonjo-Iweala, N. & Osafo-Kwaako, P. (2007). Nigeria's economic reforms: Progress and challenges. Brookings Global Economy and Development Working Paper, (6).
- Okunmadewa, F. (2011). *Poverty and welfare in Nigeria*. Ibadan: Abibis and Associates.
- Ogunleye, A. & Adeyemi, O. (2020). Poverty reduction strategies in Nigeria: A critical review of the Goodluck Jonathan administration. *Journal of African Studies*, 25(3), 87- 104.
- Zakari, F. (2021). *Poverty reduction in Nigeria: A four-point demand*. Ibadan: Abibis and Associates